

AN OPEN COLLABORATION MODEL

4 Steps for Local Partnerships in the Just Energy Transition

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

This project has received
funding from the European
Union's LIFE Programme
under grant agreement No.
101077514

CONTENT

Foreword	3
1 Creating Tandems	4
1.1 Objectives	5
1.2 A Value Driven Approach	6
1.3 Jet Pioneers	7
2 Co-Creation	9
2.1 The Four Steps of Open Collaboration	9
2.2 The Discovery Phase	11
2.3 The Dream Phase	15
2.4 The Design Phase	18
» The Role of Local Regulation	
» Dealing with Opposition and Resistance	
2.5 The Delivery Phase	22
» Result-Oriented Monitoring	
» Action-Oriented Monitoring	
3 Methods & Tools.....	25
The TANDEMS Project.....	26

FOREWORD

The TANDEM Open Collaboration Model (OCM) is more than just a framework – it is a call to action for local communities ready to drive sustainable change through meaningful partnerships. By following its four steps – Discover, Dream, Design, and Deliver – local authorities working in tandem with a local energy community can turn ambitious energy transition visions into real, lasting impact. Whether you are a local government, energy cooperative, or community leader, the OCM empowers you to build partnerships grounded in trust, shared responsibility, and tangible results.

The success stories of the TANDEM pilots that inspired the creation of the OCM show what is possible when local authorities and energy communities embrace collaboration. The OCM helped these initiatives bridge gaps between a diverse set of actors, unlocking financial, social, as well as ecological value for the community. But the true power of the OCM lies in its flexibility. It is not a one-size-fits-all solution but a living guide that adapts to your unique challenges and opportunities. With its practical tools such value network mapping, defining guiding principles, and reflexive monitoring, the OCM gives your initiative focus while remaining responsive to changing circumstances.

The energy transition is one of the defining challenges of our time, but also one of its greatest opportunities. By using the Open Collaboration Model, you can create an energy future where everyone benefits. The path is clear – so let us move forward together.”

Erik Laes
VITO

1 CREATING TANDEMMS

Local authorities and energy communities are natural allies in the just energy transition, as both work to advance the interests of citizens. By collaborating, they can pool resources and expertise to promote renewable energy, improve efficiency, and build resilient, inclusive energy systems. This partnership offers benefits like lower carbon emissions, increased energy affordability, local economic growth, energy independence, and community empowerment. The EU's 'Clean Energy for All Europeans' package highlights this role, with the Renewable Energy Directive (EU/2023/2413) recognizing local authorities as key players in energy communities, and the Energy Efficiency Directive (EU/2023/1791) stressing their importance in building renovations and responsible procurement.

The TANDEMMS project, funded by the EU LIFE programme, promotes collaboration between municipalities and citizen-led initiatives in Belgium, the Netherlands and Bulgaria. During the project (Oct 2022 to Sept 2025), pilot projects will be implemented and new energy communities established. Knowledge will be exchanged and practical strategies and concepts will be developed. These guidelines are one of the many project results.

WHAT?

The Open Collaboration Model (OCM) assists a team of pioneers in developing, designing and implementing a value network for a local energy initiative that delivers shared, multiple and collective value to the community. It focuses specifically on the role of local authorities and local energy communities in this process.

WHY?

Delivering shared, multiple and collective value to the community is vital to secure the sustainability, legitimacy, and resilience of local energy initiatives. By working together, local authorities and local energy communities can leverage their combined resources and expertise to drive the adoption of renewable energy, improve energy efficiency, and build resilient and inclusive energy systems.

HOW?

The OCM guides the team of pioneers through the 4 phases of discovering existing value networks in the community, dreaming about the values they wish to realize, (re)designing a value network for a local energy initiative and inspired by the, dream values', and delivering value to the community.

1.1 Objectives

The TANDEMS Open Collaboration Model (OCM) is designed to foster effective partnerships between local authorities and energy communities, creating shared value in the local energy transition. While other groups like social workers, civil society organizations, or private companies may play a role, the OCM focuses on local authorities and energy communities as „privileged partners“.

The nature of collaboration can vary. Some local authorities take a hands-off approach, providing financial support, meeting spaces, or bringing together community members. Others are more hands-on, participating actively as members or shareholders in energy communities, or investing in renewable energy infrastructure. Similarly, energy communities can range from passive support (e.g., promoting initiatives) to active involvement (e.g., organizing crowdfunding for renewable energy projects). There is a spectrum of options that allow collaborations to be tailored to different needs and capacities.

The OCM does not prescribe a specific type of collaboration, as long as it creates shared value. Its objectives are:

- To establish collaborative networks between local authorities and energy communities (and possibly other partners) that generate shared value.
- To help align collaborations with local needs and capacities.
- To support a flexible and evolving approach to value creation, recognizing that partnerships may shift as a project moves from concept to implementation. Collaborations may also need to take reflective pauses to reassess their direction as they progress.

1.2 A Value Driven Approach

The OCM is rooted in transition theory and is centered around the concept of the value network. A value network represents the interconnected system of actors working together to produce, distribute, and deliver value to the community. In this context, „value“ refers to the benefits or contributions each actor provides or receives within the network. These values can be material (e.g., a rooftop, solar installation, or subsidy) or immaterial (e.g., legitimacy, empowerment). They are exchanged or shared among actors to achieve mutual benefits. In local energy initiatives, the values typically fall into the following categories:

	Natural Values	Land for building renewable energy infrastructure, clean water, forests, biodiversity, and clean air.
	Infrastructure Values	The built infrastructure within a community, including buildings, roads, bridges, utilities, transportation systems, and public facilities.
	Financial Values	Monetary resources such as savings, investments, income, grants, subsidies and access to financial institutions.
	Human Development Values	Knowledge, skills, talents, and capacities of individuals within a community.
	Social Values	The relationships, networks, trust, and social cohesion within a community.
	Cultural Values	The shared values, traditions, beliefs, customs, languages, arts, and cultural heritage within a community.
	Political Values	Democratic decision-making processes, legitimate authority, and civic engagement within a community.

Overall, a value network operates as a collaborative ecosystem where various actors work together to create, deliver, and capture value, ultimately contributing to the success and sustainability of the network as a whole. The value network mapping methodology visualizes the roles fulfilled by various actors in the value network (e.g., provider of land, installer of a PV installation, operator of the electricity distribution network, etc.) and the exchanges of values between them (e.g., the provider of land leases a piece of land to a wind energy developer, who pays a monthly lease).

Some of the roles in the value network can in principle be filled in by many different actors (e.g., in a liberalized energy market, different energy supply companies can fill in the role of 'energy supplier'). In contrast to this group of interchangeable actors, there is a group of actors that cannot (easily) be replaced either because they are the only possible actor to perform a crucial role in value creation (e.g., a distribution system operator has a 'natural monopoly' for distributing electricity in a regional network) and/or because they embody the core values of the entire network. In the OCM, we call the latter actors the JET-pioneers.

1.3 Jet Pioneers

The OCM's target users are Just Energy Transition (JET)-pioneer teams, core groups driving the creation of shared, collective value in the energy transition. The term „JET“ conveys two key messages:

- **Complexity of the Energy Transition:** The energy transition is like rebuilding an airplane in mid-flight – it requires a comprehensive transformation of energy production, distribution, and use, without disrupting the constant supply. JET-pioneers must be aware of the challenges and keep their actions feasible.

- **Just and Inclusive Transition:** JET-pioneer teams aim to accelerate the energy transition by saving energy, using it efficiently, and replacing fossil fuels with renewables, while ensuring that the benefits are fairly distributed. They are committed to:
 - » **Multiple value creation:** Generating social, economic, and ecological value.
 - » **Shared value creation:** Ensuring fair distribution of benefits within the community.
 - » **Collective value creation:** Fostering collaboration based on co-creation and equitable participation.

A JET-pioneer team can come from any sector – local government, civil society, or other actors involved in the energy transition. Leadership can emerge from various areas, as long as the team has access to essential resources (e.g., time, expertise, funding, networks) and the ability to bring together local actors, such as citizens, organizations, or public officials, around a shared goal.

Examples of JET-pioneer teams:

- A team of local government officials working to unite the community and expedite the energy transition.
- A civil society group partnering with local authorities to tackle an energy-related issue and launch a community energy initiative.
- A social housing organization focused on reducing energy poverty and aligning with local climate goals.

The composition of the JET-pioneer team can evolve over time, from a small group with initial ideas to an established network delivering value through concrete energy initiatives. The team's primary role is to spark and sustain collaboration throughout the process.

BELOW:

During the TANDEMS meeting in Vienna (April 2024) the OCM was discussed by the members of the consortium.

2 CO-CREATION

On the following pages you will find practice-orientated steps, terms and working concepts that will help you to create the right environment for co-creation.

2.1 The Four Steps of Open Collaboration

The OCM guides the JET-pioneer team through the process of designing or redesigning a value network focused on creating and delivering shared value through a local energy initiative. It consists of four steps or phases:

- DISCOVER** | The team explores and analyzes strengths, resources, and opportunities within the community. This involves mapping the current value network, identifying key actors, and understanding community needs related to the energy transition. The goal is to gain a comprehensive understanding of the local context.
- DREAM** | Building on insights from the Discovery Phase, the team envisions an ideal future for the energy initiative. Through brainstorming and visioning exercises, they define shared values, set ambitious goals, and create a clear vision of what success looks like, inspiring motivation and commitment.
- DESIGN** | The team translates the vision into concrete plans and strategies. This includes defining roles, allocating resources, and establishing collaboration mechanisms. The focus is on aligning the project with the overall vision, addressing challenges, and maximizing opportunities for value creation.
- DELIVER** | In this phase, the team implements the plans, mobilizes resources, and works with partners to execute the initiative. They monitor progress, make necessary adjustments, and focus on achieving tangible results that contribute to the local energy transition.

It's important to note that these phases don't have to be followed in strict order. Depending on the situation, some steps might be skipped or revisited. For example, if a project is well-established, the team may move directly to the Delivery Phase. The process is iterative, and teams should regularly reflect and adjust, even revisiting earlier steps and phases to ensure the initiative is still aligned with its goals.

Meet BART

Taking on the role of a JET-pioneer team can feel overwhelming, but luckily, you will have a fictional assistant along your side: BART – the Boundary-spanning Action Reflexive Tutor helps you by asking the right questions:

- BART helps the team **step beyond their own organization or sector** to build and maintain networks that bridge gaps and bring people from diverse backgrounds together in a co-creative setting.
- BART ensures the team **stays focused on action**, avoiding over-analysis that could hinder progress.
- BART encourages the team to **critically assess their role, perspectives, and biases** within the system to enhance their transformative impact
- Rather than providing ready-made answers, BART asks **guiding questions, encouraging the team to explore, think critically, and develop their own solutions**. The guidance is tailored to the specific project stage and context.

In summary, BART systematically guides the JET-pioneer team through the four stages of designing a value network for energy transition initiatives, using questions, tools, and examples to help the team find the right answers.

2.2 The Discovery Phase

The Discovery Phase of the OCM helps the JET-pioneer team identify clear opportunities to deliver shared value through an energy transition initiative. This is done by analyzing the existing value network and conducting a SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats).

WHAT?

The Discovery Phase of the OCM helps the JET-pioneer team to discover concrete opportunities for providing shared, multiple and collective value to the community through a collaboration between local authorities and local communities.

WHY?

The Discovery Phase in the OCM is crucial as it sets the foundation for the entire process by uncovering existing strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats within the local energy context. It enables the JET-pioneer team to build on positive aspects and address the current weaknesses of local energy transition initiatives.

HOW?

BART assists the JET-pioneer team in mapping the current value network by conducting interviews, surveys, or group discussions, with a focus on overall value creation, actor engagement and local governance. This process allows the JET-pioneer team to uncover the problem they wish to solve.

WHEN?

It is essential to engage in the Discovery Phase when there is a need to understand the current state of the local energy transition, identify strengths, weaknesses and opportunities, and lay the groundwork for envisioning a positive future direction.

Teams often enter this phase with a preliminary idea, informed by resources like local climate and energy action plans or assessments of renewable energy opportunities (e.g., land for wind farms or rooftops for solar panels).

Common scopes for community energy initiatives include:

- Establishing community-owned PV projects for electricity generation (with self-consumption or energy sharing).
- Building and operating community-owned wind farms.
- Improving energy efficiency in homes, businesses, and public buildings.
- Ensuring vulnerable customers have access to affordable, locally-generated renewable energy.
- Developing district heating systems for neighborhoods.

- Creating renewable energy infrastructure for sustainable business parks.
- Building local microgrids or virtual power plants for energy resilience.
- Educating the community on energy savings and renewable technologies.
- Promoting electric vehicle adoption with charging stations.
- Investing in battery storage systems for excess renewable energy.
- Setting up biogas facilities to convert organic waste into renewable energy.

After selecting the scope for the energy transition initiative, the JET-pioneer team maps out the existing value network, which represents the current way value is delivered. The NEXUS tool on value network mapping can help here. For example, in a campaign promoting energy-efficient home retrofits, key actors might include local authorities, energy efficiency organizations, construction companies, and utilities. Local authorities might provide resources, while energy organizations offer expertise, construction companies implement retrofits, and utilities provide incentives.

Scan QR Code for the
Nexus Value Network
Mapping Tutorial

Mapping the current value network is crucial for several reasons:

- **Understanding dynamics:** It offers a clear overview of how actors interact, revealing inefficiencies or bottlenecks.
- **Identifying key actors and roles:** It clarifies who contributes to value creation and their dependencies.
- **Visualizing interdependencies:** The map highlights connections and critical dependencies within the value chain.
- **Spotting innovation opportunities:** It can reveal new partnerships, roles, or technologies to enhance value creation.
- **Informing design decisions:** The map guides decisions for improvement, helping to set priorities and strategies.
- **Engaging other actors:** The map promotes engagement and alignment among stakeholders by providing a shared understanding.

This phase concludes with a SWOT analysis of the current value network, supported by BART's guiding questions to help assess the roles of local actors and governance.

BART's Guiding Questions:

1. Are certain local actors excluded from value creation?

Identify if any groups are currently marginalized and not benefiting from the value creation. Understand why they are excluded to address this in a potential redesign.

2. Does the current value network create economic, ecological, and social value?

Evaluate whether the value network equally supports social, economic, and ecological value creation, or if one area is stronger than the others.

3. Does each actor receive a fair share of the value created?

Assess whether each actor is fairly compensated in relation to their contribution and role in the network.

4. What are the opportunities and threats to the current value network?

Consider how the network may be affected by actors joining, leaving, or changing their level of engagement, and assess its resilience to these changes.

TANDEMUS

At the end of the Discovery Phase, the JET-pioneer team should clearly define an opportunity to deliver shared value through an energy transition initiative. **This opportunity should:**

- Be clear and specific, avoiding ambiguity.
- Have a focused scope, without being too broad.
- Align with the team's concerns and priorities.
- Be achievable within available resources and time constraints.
- Reflect the needs and priorities of the local community to ensure engagement.
- Show an understanding of the local policy context.

Example:

The collaboration between the City of Mechelen and the local energy cooperative Klimaan took shape through the Otterbeek pilot project, aimed at generating and sharing solar energy among social housing tenants. This partnership was driven by a shared commitment to tackling energy poverty while advancing the city's climate goals. The social housing company provided institutional support by granting access to social housing rooftops, while Klimaan mobilized citizen investments and managed the technical aspects of the project.

What made this partnership particularly effective was its grounded understanding of local policy frameworks and its alignment with the city's sustainability targets. All parties approached the collaboration with a realistic perspective, acknowledging financial, logistical, and regulatory constraints. They also prioritized community engagement by ensuring that tenants of the social housing complex would benefit directly through reduced energy bills and active participation in the project.

By combining Klimaan's grassroots expertise with the city of Mechelen's institutional capacity, the partnership successfully bridged policy-driven goals with community-led action, creating a replicable model for sustainable, socially inclusive energy initiatives.

» **Further reading:** <https://coop.klimaan.be/project/otterbeek>

Additionally, the Discovery Phase may lead to expanding the JET-pioneer team by involving new actors from the value network. With a clear opportunity defined, the (expanded) team can move on to the next phase.

Members of the TANDEM project team during a meeting in Mechelen (November 2022).

2.3 The Dream Phase

The Dream Phase focuses on defining the core values that guide decisions and actions for the community energy initiative. These values act as a moral compass, providing clear direction toward the final goal. For example, the JET-pioneer team might adopt principles like those of the International Cooperative Alliance. These values not only establish leadership and identity but also differentiate the initiative from traditional energy approaches. Clear guiding values help communicate the team's mission, attract a broader audience, and bring in new actors who share the same values.

WHAT?

The Dream Phase entails collectively imagining and articulating a shared vision of what the community energy initiative could look like in its most positive and desirable form.

WHY?

The purpose of the Dream Phase is to inspire and motivate local actors by focusing on possibilities, potential, and positive aspirations. By envisioning a compelling future vision, local actors are encouraged to think creatively and ambitiously about the possibilities for a just energy transition initiative within the community.

HOW?

BART facilitates the dream phase through participatory processes such as visioning workshops, brainstorming sessions on values, and storytelling exercises. Local actors are encouraged to share their dreams and aspirations for the community's energy future, with an emphasis on exploring innovative ideas and bold solutions.

WHEN?

The Dream Phase serves as a bridge between the exploration of current realities and the co-creation of a shared vision for the future, providing a positive and forward-looking perspective to guide subsequent planning and action.

BELOW:
PV-panels on roof tops in the Otterbeek neighbourhood of Mechelen.

BART's Guidance for Dreaming

/17/

Guiding values for the JET-pioneer team should be collectively agreed upon and provide clear direction for the community energy initiative. This process is iterative and cannot be completed in one session. It's important to involve key actors from the value network in workshops or forums to co-create these values. BART's guidance can be useful for engaging local authorities in this process.

1. What values should the energy community generate for all stakeholders involved?

This question helps identify the intended impacts across key sustainability dimensions, ensuring a holistic value approach.

2. How can different stakeholders (e.g., residents, local businesses, municipalities) meaningfully participate in decision-making and benefit from the initiative?

This question helps to ensure equitable participation, fostering shared responsibility and collective ownership.

3. What mechanisms should be in place to ensure fair distribution of financial, social, and energy-related benefits among all community members?

This question focuses on transparency and accountability in how resources and returns are shared.

4. How can the initiative create long-term community value while adapting to changing local needs and policy environments?

This encourages forward-looking strategies that balance current impacts with future sustainability and resilience.

Scan QR Code for the
Nexus Guiding
Principles Tutorial

The NEXUS tool for guiding principles can help define the core values that guide decisions and actions for energy initiatives by facilitating group discussions. Examples of guiding values include:

Economic Value:

- **Cost savings:** Lower energy bills through collective energy purchasing, efficiency measures, and renewable energy generation.
- **Revenue generation:** Income by selling energy to the grid or through energy trading.

Social Value:

- **Community empowerment:** Residents take control of their energy future, fostering pride and self-reliance.
- **Social cohesion:** Collaborative decision-making strengthens community bonds and trust.
- **Energy equity:** Access to affordable, clean energy for all, regardless of income.

Ecological Value:

- **Carbon reduction:** Renewable energy projects help cut greenhouse gas emissions and improve air quality.

- **Resource conservation:** Energy efficiency and renewable technologies reduce consumption, minimize waste, and preserve resources.

The outcome of the Dream Phase in the OCM is a shared vision and a future value map, showing the ideal outcomes, roles, and values the JET-pioneer team aims to achieve. This collective vision serves as a guiding beacon for future planning and actions in the energy initiative. To complete this step, the team should document their insights in an engaging storyline, using tools like the storytelling canvas. Storytelling helps simplify complex ideas by framing them in relatable, concrete narratives, making it easier to communicate key insights and lessons.

Example:

The story of AGEM starts in September 2009, when 8 municipalities of the Achterhoek region signed the 'Akkoord van Groenlo' (the 'Groenlo Agreement'). The main ambition of this agreement was to become an energy neutral region on the long term. It also set out a CO2 reduction goal of -50% in 2020 (compared to 1990 levels), whereas the national ambition at that time was -30%. The agreement also included very concrete short-term goals. Setting these targets gave clear form to the long-term goals and aspirations, making them more tangible and essential for driving action.

The initial agreement was further extended by inviting local actors (from education, private sector, etc.) to join the 'Table of Groenlo,' which was described as the moment when the 'Achterhoek community feeling' emerged. EU project funding was acquired to develop an action plan and lobbying for further financial support towards the Dutch Ministry of Economic Affairs was initiated. The Ministry however refused to support the initiative (calling it 'entirely unrealistic'), which further strengthened the resolve of the Table of Groenlo to intensify their efforts to 'do it all by themselves.'

» **Further reading:** <https://www.agem.nl>

BELOW:

AGEM hosted a TANDEMS project meeting in Doetinchem (December 2023).

2.4 The Design Phase

In the Design Phase, the focus shifts to creating actionable plans that turn the vision from the Dream Phase into reality. The JET-pioneer team identifies the actors needed for the future value network, establishes governance requirements, and develops strategies to address potential resistance.

WHAT?

The Design Phase focuses on developing concrete plans and actions to realize the desired future state envisioned during the Dream Phase. It involves identifying specific goals, objectives, and actions that align with the values of the community energy initiative.

WHY?

The purpose of the Design Phase is to bridge the gap between vision and action. By translating aspirations into tangible actions, the design step empowers the JET-pioneer team to turn their vision into reality and drive meaningful progress in the community energy initiative.

HOW?

BART gives practical guidance that helps the JET-pioneer team to select the right (community) actors and local authorities for filling in the roles of the desired future value network. It also explains the role of local governance and highlights strategies to counter resistance.

WHEN?

The Design Phase marks the transition from envisioning to action planning, signaling the beginning of the implementation step where concrete steps are taken to realize the desired future state of the community energy initiative.

By the end of this step, the team will have:

- Identified the actors who will fill key roles in the value network.
- Determined how the future value network will operate.
- Outlined the initial steps for implementation.

After redesigning the value network, the JET-pioneer team should carefully evaluate the list of potential actors for the new roles. A key risk is the rapid influx of diverse actors – enthusiastic partners, volunteers, but also opportunists and free riders – once ideas are shared. While initial excitement is common, the network's success depends on sustained effort from committed actors. Therefore, it's crucial to identify those who truly align with the shared values and goals.

Ask yourselves:

- For which actors is the shared value critically important?
- Which actors are genuinely committed to creating this value collectively?

Based on the answers to these questions, the JET-pioneer team should be able to assign potential partners to one of the following three categories:

- **Core actors:** without having these partners on board, it will be impossible to realize the new value network. Therefore, it is essential to focus on building good relationships between these partners, based on mutual trust, and on continuity of the collaboration.
- **Key actors:** these are partners that are needed for specific tasks or at specific stages of implementing the new value network, e.g., because they have specific skills or expertise. For these partners, it should be clear how, when and for how long they will be involved.
- **Supporting actors:** these partners play a valuable complementary role in the collaboration by enhancing the value network through activities such as promoting it to a broader audience, providing sponsorship, or offering indirect support.

Having classified the actors, a series of one-on-one talks or workshops with the potential actors should give the JET-pioneer team an answer to another set of guiding questions.

BART's Guidance for Designing

- Which parts of your **value network** can you **manage and organize** yourself (e.g., the JET-pioneer team), and which knowledge, experience, and skills do you need to acquire from the outside?
- Are the guiding values of the community energy initiative really **part of the 'DNA'** of the (potential) partner? Or are they just willing to contribute because of a (temporary) alignment of interests?
- Is there a **willingness to collaborate** on solutions to problems in the value network, even if these problems do not relate specifically to the envisaged role of the (potential) partner?
- Is there a **commitment in the long term**? Can you establish and maintain a relationship with the (potential) partner?

The Role of Local Regulation

After redesigning the value network, the JET-pioneer team should review the regulatory implications of the new network. Governance affects the value network through:

- **Institutional roles:** Institutional actors often operate under official mandates governed by rules and regulations. Sometimes regulations require specific roles within the network. For example, under EU energy market rules, every customer has the right to choose their energy supplier, making energy supply companies a mandatory part of any energy community's value network.
- **Rules governing transactions:** Value exchanges between actors are regulated by formal or informal rules that outline obligations, deadlines, verification methods, and conflict resolution processes.

Dealing with Opposition and Resistance

Next to the actors of the (re)designed value network, it is also important for the JET-pioneer team to think about potential adversaries – i.e., opponents that stand to lose in case the (re)designed value network becomes a success. Here, we can distinguish between:

- **Passive Opponents:** Passive opponents are opposed to the initiative but are not actively engaged in efforts to block or hinder its progress. They may express their opposition through passive resistance, such as expressing concerns or reservations but not taking further action to oppose the initiative actively. Passive opponents may be less vocal or visible in their opposition compared to active opponents.
- **Active Opponents:** Active opponents are actively engaged in opposing the initiative and may take deliberate actions to obstruct, undermine, or challenge its implementation. They may organize protests, lobby decision-makers, file legal challenges, or mobilize public opposition to the initiative. Active opponents are more visible and vocal in their opposition, actively working to prevent the initiative from moving forward.
- **Leading Opponents:** Leading opponents are not only actively opposing the initiative but also hold significant influence or leadership positions within the stakeholder community. They may be influential community leaders, elected officials, prominent organizations, or key decision-makers whose opposition carries substantial weight and can significantly impact the initiative's prospects for success. Leading opponents may have the ability to mobilize broader support for their opposition efforts and shape public opinion or policy decisions related to the initiative.

The outcome of the design phase is a comprehensive blueprint for the future value network. This includes the identification and selection of key actors, a roadmap for addressing potential opposition, a clear understanding of the governance implications, and a series of concrete follow-up actions. These actions, ranging from developing innovative business models to fostering community engagement, will guide the JET-pioneer team towards the successful implementation of the desired future state.

Example:

ZuidtrAnt successfully completed the Design step by translating its long-term renovation vision into a practical value network through well-defined roles, strategic partnerships, and action-oriented plans.

Klimaatwerf, the driving non-profit behind Burenwerf, established a structured partnership model involving municipalities, energy cooperatives, and local contractors. This included categorizing key actors such as municipalities providing access to neighborhoods, energy cooperatives ensuring operational management, and contractors delivering renovation services. Governance requirements were addressed by formalizing agreements with 14 municipalities, ensuring political support, administrative efficiency, and transparent public reporting.

Recognizing potential resistance, Burenwerf proactively engaged municipal teams through cross-departmental collaborations and organized resident information sessions to build local trust. First steps toward implementation included launching renovation trajectories in municipalities like Zoersel, supported by active neighborhood committees and volunteer energy coaches. This multi-stakeholder approach secured long-term municipal engagement and established a sustainable revenue model, demonstrating a clear path from design to actionable implementation.

Further reading: <https://www.klimaatwerf.be>

2.5 The Delivery Phase

Once strategies are defined in the Design Phase, the Delivery Phase helps the JET-pioneer team monitor their effectiveness in reaching the desired future state. Monitoring is essential for ensuring success and achieving outcomes. The OCM uses two approaches: result-oriented and action-oriented monitoring.

- **Result-oriented monitoring** tracks progress and impact through key performance indicators (KPIs).
- **Action-oriented monitoring** helps the team reflect on activities and ensure short-term actions align with long-term goals.

WHAT?

The Delivery Phase involves the implementation of the strategies and actions identified and planned during the Design Phase. It focuses on monitoring the execution of strategies, mobilization of resources, and engagement of actors to achieve the desired goals and objectives of the community energy project.

WHY?

By monitoring the execution of planned actions, the JET pioneer team can make sure that the community energy initiative moves closer to achieving its vision for a sustainable energy future.

HOW?

By implementing a reflexive monitoring strategy, members of the JET-pioneer team collaborate to deploy resources, monitor progress, and overcome obstacles encountered during implementation.

WHEN?

The Delivery Phase follows the Design Phase and begins once plans and strategies have been finalized. It continues throughout the implementation of actions needed to realize the desired future value network, with ongoing monitoring, evaluation, and adjustment as needed to ensure progress.

RESULT-ORIENTED MONITORING

Result-oriented monitoring tracks progress toward predefined targets, using a structured plan-monitor-evaluate cycle. Key performance indicators (KPIs) are used to assess whether the initiative is meeting its goals. This method provides a systematic way to evaluate success, offering a clear understanding of achieved outcomes compared to the original objectives. The focus is on ensuring the project stays on track and reaches its set targets.

ACTION-ORIENTED MONITORING

Action-oriented, or reflexive monitoring, takes a more adaptive approach. Rather than being a separate task, it integrates into the ongoing project process, evolving as strategies and targets shift. This participative method involves stakeholders in collective learning and adaptation, ensuring strategies remain relevant as circumstances change. It also emphasizes shared responsibility and explores systemic change.

Tools for Action-Oriented Monitoring:

- **Learning History Workshop:** Reflects on significant events, mapping them on a timeline to extract valuable lessons and insights. This reflection helps define and monitor new actions.
- **Systemic Iceberg Model:** Identifies deeper, transformative learning questions that address systemic issues, not just surface problems.
- **Bullet Journal:** Logs events in real-time or retrospectively, categorizing insights to visualize systemic patterns.
- **Dynamic Learning Agenda:** Tracks critical turning points, linking long-term goals to short-term actions. This agenda evolves over time, enabling ongoing adjustments based on lessons learned.

These tools foster a proactive, flexible approach to monitoring, focusing on continuous learning and adaptation.

Completing the Delivery step marks the culmination of the structured implementation process. During this step, the JET-pioneer team systematically monitors the execution of actions from the Design step to achieve the envisioned future of the community energy initiative.

Scan QR Code for the Nexus Learning History Workshop

Scan QR Code for the Systemic Iceberg Model

Scan QR Code for the Systemic Bullet Journal

The TANDEMS consortium meeting in Vienna (April 2024).

Example:

The successful launch of the energy community in Gabrovo was driven by a combination of strong political support, innovative financing, and strategic partnerships. The mayor's commitment, along with that of other local authorities, played a pivotal role, enabling the project to move forward despite an unclear national regulatory framework.

Public-private collaboration proved essential, with the municipality providing rooftop space for a PV installation while citizens and small businesses contributed private funds. This partnership unlocked financial potential beyond the limits of municipal budgets. Ensuring inclusive financial participation was another key success factor: citizens could invest amounts ranging from €250 to €2,500, making the project accessible to people with varying economic capacities and fostering a collective sense of ownership.

The project also benefited from legal and administrative simplicity by operating under an existing legal framework typically used by businesses, bypassing complex administrative procedures that might have caused delays. Lastly, a transparent business model built trust among potential investors. A clear business case analysis detailing costs, expected returns, and risks reassured citizens and secured the investments, even in the face of uncertain future electricity prices. This comprehensive approach demonstrates how thoughtful design and governance can pave the way for innovative and inclusive energy projects.

» **Further reading:** <https://www.rescoop.eu/news-and-events/stories/september-success-story-a-bulgarian-municipality-embracing-community-energy>

3 METHODS & TOOLS

This guideline provides an initial overview of the Open Collaboration Model (OCM) when setting up collaborative energy projects with the participation of municipalities and citizen-led initiatives. For more detailed information on this and more detailed explanations of the methodological and content-related approach, we recommend taking a look at the Deliverable Report 2.1 'Blueprint **Design of an Open Collaboration Model**', which is available on the project website:

- https://lifetandems.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/TANDEMS-D2.1-Open-Collaboration-Model_final.pdf

Practical tools and information can also be found on the **NEXUS Learn Website**:

- <https://coda.io/@vito/nexuslearn/transition-tools-10>

Scan QR code for the
NEXUS tool collection

Co-funded by
the European Union

This project has received
funding from the European
Union's LIFE Programme
under grant agreement
No. 101077514

The TANDEMS Project:

Encouraging the collaboration between municipalities and energy cooperatives for a just and accelerated energy transition

The TANDEMS project (2022-2025) aims to encourage the development of energy communities as vehicles for energy transition through including citizens in every step, engage local governments and policy makers to support and invest in these communities.

AUTHORS

Oikoplus GmbH
Millergasse 37/3 | 1060 Vienna | Austria
VITO – Vlaamse Instelling voor
Technologisch Onderzoek
Boeretang 200 | BE-2400 Mol | Belgium

GRAPHIC DESIGN & ILLUSTRATION

Sarah Strobl

PHOTOGRAPHY & ICONOGRAPHY

TANDEMS
Marten Boekelo
Oikoplus GmbH
Freepik
Klimaan

PARTNERS

Kamp C
Duneworks BV
Agem BV
City of Mechelen
Klimaan Csvo
Zuidtrant
EnEffect
Municipality of Burgas
Municipality of Gabrovo
Oikoplus GmbH

TANDEMS

www.lifetandems.eu

©2025

